

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SULEMANA****FIRST NAME: AMINU****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (MSWord – office 365 on MacOS Ventura 13.2.1)

List 5 to 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Process of writing academic essays (EUCLID 2021, 7-14)
2. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 25- 32)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-39)
4. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 41-42)
5. Chicago Manual Style (EUCLID 2021, 44-57)

WRITING ACADEMIC ESSAY

1)INTRODUCTION

In reading the course pack for ACA-401D period one (1), I have rediscovered myself as a student who needs to pay attention to the fundamentals of the English language and prepare adequately for the journey that lies ahead of me through the course of my study with EUCLID. The course ACA-401D has given me a different perspective on academic writing and has turned out to be the course I should have taken while studying for my master's program at the university in Ghana.

I have also watched the course videos on how to format a response paper, the use of styles, citations, and referencing delivered by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck, and how to review a response paper delivered by Dr. Kabiru Gulma. I must admit that the videos have given me a better understanding of what is required in writing a response paper.

In this response paper, I discussed the concepts, including the process of writing academic essays and using American and British English, plagiarism, style guide, and the Chicago Manual of Style.

2) PROCESS OF WRITING ACADEMIC ESSAY

Academic essays acknowledge the contribution of other works through citations and references. It usually advances a new argument that provides proof to claim or otherwise based on the findings. In writing academic essays, I understand that you must adhere to the basic process, which includes starting early enough to have time to analyze the topic properly and read widely to broaden your knowledge, define the scope of the work, and find possible answers to all the research questions, draw a plan to guide and organize your initial thoughts and ideas (EUCLID 2021, 7–9).

After researching and organizing your thoughts around the topic, the next step is to create a structure or framework to guide you in producing a first draft. The draft should include an introduction, body, and conclusion. The introduction of academic writing should generally give an overview of the subject matter, narrow it down to the claim, and clearly state the claim being investigated. The body is the part where the main ideas are developed into constructive arguments where the writer provides evidence, including examples, to support his arguments or claims. It is important to structure each idea logically by organizing the body of the writing into paragraphs. The conclusion summarizes the ideas in the body while emphasizing the writers' position on the research question or claim (EUCLID 2021, 10). I understand that you must develop the body of your academic writing before writing your conclusion and the introduction.

It is important to give credibility to academic writings by acknowledging the contribution of other writers; therefore, using citations and references in all academic writings guides against academic dishonesty or plagiarism.

3) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

America has forged strong political and economic influence after World War II. Its dominance in the world has largely influenced world English being spoken today internationally. American and British English are the two most widely spoken worldwide; perhaps the difference in pronunciation, spelling, and usage between the two is not easily noticeable (EUCLID 2021, 25). One noticeable difference between American and British English is the use of periods, commas, and quotation marks according to EUCLID(2021, 31); this is extremely important when using British English, inverted commas are used for all quotations, while quotation marks are used in American English.

I have never noticed the difference between American and British English, as it is used interchangeably in Ghana. Ghana is a member of the Commonwealth; we are expected to use British English as our schooling system follows the British system. However, due to globalization and the dominance of the United States, Ghana has embraced the two, and it is used interchangeably.

During my interaction with how to write a response paper and the short video, I understood that EUCLID does not choose the English the student should use but

recommends that students adopt one type of English variant and use it throughout their writing (EUCLID 2021, 4).

4) PLAGIARISM

In academic writing, acknowledging the contribution of other writers or the source of information is very important. According to EUCLID (2021, 34), “when a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of the information,” it constitutes plagiarism. Other acts that constitute plagiarism include paraphrasing or quoting directly and copying and pasting other people’s work without crediting the author.

Plagiarism constitutes an academic offense and can lead to the rejection of the writer’s work. To avoid plagiarism, one needs to properly cite the author or the source of information. EUCLID emphasizes two critical things to note when citing a document; these are the in-text citations and the list of works cited. When using the in-text citation, it is appropriate to indicate the author’s name, the year of publication, and the page number for which the information can be found. While the list of works cited provides complete, detailed information of the work used (EUCLID 2021, 38).

5) STYLE GUIDE

EUCLID (2021, 41) states, “A style is a means of documenting your approach to certain elements of writing that need to be consistent.” The writing style emphasizes the ability of the writer to be consistent and coherent with his writing output and, therefore, the need to follow published guidelines that many writers have contributed to align with the style of the publishing company or website associated with the writings.

It is important to note that there are many schools of thought on style for written English; however, the use of punctuation and correct grammar have been well established. Reading the course pack for ACA-401D, I understand that EUCLID accepts any writing style, but preferably, the Chicago rules (Turabian) and American English are recommended (EUCLID 2021, 41).

6) CHICAGO MANUAL STYLE

According to EUCLID (2021, 44), the Chicago Manual of Style documents the process of formatting books and research papers. It provides essential guidelines for the use of abbreviations, acronyms, capitalization, quotations, numbers and dates, and page formatting, as well as the use of end/footnotes.

For example, in academic writing, abbreviations/acronyms should only start a sentence if there is no other way to write it. Writers should use fewer abbreviations in

academic writing because readers will lose track of abbreviations if used often, especially unfamiliar abbreviations (EUCLID 2021, 44).

The writer's style is crucial in academic writing to provide consistency and coherence in his output.

7) CONCLUSION

Essays intended for academic purposes have clear guidelines that must be followed. In writing essays, the writer must understand the process and adopt one form of language and style of writing to provide some consistency. He should be mindful of plagiarism and provide proper citations and references to avoid it. Furthermore, the writer must adopt a style of formatting his work.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

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